

Influence of Conscientiousness Personality Trait on Menopause Crises

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Abstract: Conscientiousness is a higher order personality trait that incorporates ideals such as competence, orderliness and self-control. Conscientiousness concerns the way in which we control, regulate and direct our impulses. This study examined the influence of conscientiousness personality traits on menopause crisis for public primary schools' female teachers in Laikipia County. The study utilized ex post facto research design because it was not possible or acceptable to manipulate the characteristics of human participants. The study was based on the Big Five theory of personality. The target populations were 600 female teachers, 50 teacher counselors, 5 Sub County Directors of Education in the Ministry of Education, giving a total of 655 respondents in Laikipia County. The researcher used stratified sampling, two stage clustered sampling, random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. The sample of the study was 289 respondents. The statistical analysis entailed the computation of frequencies and percentages. The Findings revealed that conscientiousness personality trait have a statistically significant influence on menopause crisis with a Linear Regression analysis where by ($r^2=0.650$; $p>0.033$) which was significant at 0.05 level of confidence. From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that conscientiousness personality trait influence menopause crisis. It is recommended that counselors should aim at helping menopausal female teachers deal with their emotional instability.

Keywords: conscientiousness, personality traits, menopause crisis, big five theory of personality.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conscientious-oriented people have been shown to have personality traits such as wisdom, love for beauty, intellectual curiosity, independent judgment, artistry, flexibility and a high sensitivity toward positive and negative emotions (Kaufman, 2013). In addition, people with high levels of conscientiousness appear to be able to regulate emotion and recover more easily from negative stimuli possibly by reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression (Javaras, 2012). According to trait theory research, people who are high in this trait may perceive a need for services but feel they must take care of their problems themselves.

A study by Cheng-Hsiang (2015) on the relationship between personality characteristics and sleep quality in menopausal women found a reverse correlation between overall sleep quality and conscientiousness, though this correlation was not significant. People that have a high degree of conscientiousness are reliable and prompt. Traits include being organized, methodical and thorough. Impulses are not inherently bad; occasionally time constraints require a snap decision and acting on our first impulse can be an effective response. Likewise, in times of play rather than work, acting spontaneously and impulsively can be fun. Impulsive individuals can be seen by others as colourful, fun-to-be-with and zany. Conscientious individuals avoid trouble and achieve high levels of success through purposeful planning and persistence. They are also positively regarded by others as intelligent and reliable. On the negative side, they can be compulsive perfectionists and workaholics. Furthermore, extremely conscientious individuals might be regarded as stuffy and boring. Unconscientious people may be criticized for their unreliability, lack of ambition and failure to stay within the lines, but they will experience many short-lived pleasures and they will never be called stuffy.

2. RESEARCH DESIGN

The study utilized *ex post facto* correlational research design. *Ex- post facto* research can be viewed as experimental research in reverse. *Ex post facto* research is ideal for conducting social research when is not possible or acceptable to manipulate the characteristics of human participants. It is a substitute for true experimental research and can be used to test hypotheses about cause and effect or correlational relationships, where it is not practical or ethical to apply a true experimental or even a quasi-experimental design (Simon & Goes, 2013). The research design was appropriate for this study since the independent variables were not be manipulated to establish their effects on the dependent variables. The research design was adopted in order to determine the influence of the independent variables under study that is neurotic personality related characteristics and female teacher's menopause crises (the dependent variable). A structured questionnaire was used to gather raw data from the female teachers in public primary schools in the study area. The questionnaire comprised items on the female teachers' neurotic personality traits in relation to menopause crises.

3. STUDY RESULTS

Results of descriptive analysis of data on conscientiousness personality traits is presented in the following section. The respondents were guided by a Linkert scale in which 1 represented Strongly Disagree (SD), 2 represented Disagree (D), 3 represented Neutral (N), 4 represented Agree (A) and 5 represented Strongly Agree (SA).

Table 1: Descriptive Results on Conscientiousness Personality Trait

CODE	Statements	1=SD	2=D	3=N	4=A	5=SA
C1	I finish what I start	5.7% (12)	15.3% (32)	13.4% (28)	45.9% (96)	19.6% (41)
C2	I always know what I am doing	5.7% (12)	11.5% (24)	23.9% (50)	37.3% (78)	5.7% (45)
C3	I mess things up	33.5% (70)	37.8% (79)	16.3% (34)	7.7% (16)	4.8% (10)
C4	I postpone decisions	20.1% (42)	17.7% (37)	22.0% (46)	36.4% (76)	3.8% (8)
C5	I like order	5.7% (12)	6.7% (14)	10.5% (22)	41.6% (87)	35.4% (74)
C6	I am not bothered by disorder	33.5% (70)	45.9% (96)	10.0% (21)	5.7% (12)	4.8% (10)

The results posted in table 1 revealed that the respondents agreed on all items except two. The two items were 'I mess things up', where 43% agreed while 17.2% were not sure while 'I am not bothered by disorder' 10.5% agreed while 79.4% disagreed, an implication that menopausal women are not affected by situations that affect order as they are able to organize themselves. Further the findings revealed that 40.2% agreed that they postpone decisions while 37.8% were not sure. Another 65.5% revealed that they finish what they start while 13.4% were not sure. This is an indication that female teachers in menopause transition are capable of meeting deadlines. This corroborates with the findings of Afridi, (2017) that menopause exhibit signs such as: difficulty focusing on daily tasks, forgetfulness, losing one's train of thought while reading or talking and unclear or fuzzy thought processes. Marcin, (2017) further bolds out that though menopausal symptoms vary with individuals, there are some common symptoms such as night sweats , weight gain, thinning hair, memory lapses and difficulty in focus and concentration as a result of "brain fog". A majority (77 %) agreed that they like order while 10% were neutral. Further, the results revealed that 71.3% disagreed that they mess things up while 16.3% were neutral. It therefore implies that menopausal female teachers in the study area do not tend to mess things up but they are orderly.

Table 2: Female Teachers' Means on Influence of Conscientiousness to Menopause Crisis

CODE	Statements	Mean	SD
C1	I finish what I start	3.58	1.137
C2	I always know what I am doing	3.57	1.120
C3	I mess things up	2.12	1.107
C4	I postpone decisions	2.86	1.219
C5	I like order	3.94	1.117
C6	I am not bothered by disorder	2.02	1.049

The six items in table 2 were measured using Likert scale of 1 to 5 where the lowest 1 represented Strongly Disagree and the highest 5 represented Strongly Agree. A mean of 2.5 to 5.0 represented high influence while a mean of less than 2.5 meant less influence. The six items indicated that the means ranged from 2.02 (SD=1.049) to 3.94 (SD=1.117). Most of the means were above 2.5 meaning that majority of the respondents agreed with the statements. However, there were two items that had low means 'I am not bothered by disorder' 2.02 (SD=1.049) and 'I mess things up' 2.12 (SD=1.107). This means that most of the respondents disagreed with the statements. The SD were high as per the statements 1.049 to 1.219 which is an indication that there was a high variation of the responses to the items.

4. CONCLUSIONS

There was a strong relationship between conscientiousness and menopause crises where ($r^2=0.650$; $p>0.033$) which was significant at 0.05. The results of the findings indicate there was a significant difference between conscientiousness and menopause crises. The findings concluded that the treatment of menopausal women requires paying close attention to the personality of menopausal women to achieve effective treatment.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The schools' administrators should aim at helping menopausal female teachers to feel less threatened, less overwhelmed and more in control of their emotions and moods. Female teachers in menopause transition should understand their personality characteristics so that they can understand themselves and cope with stresses brought by menopause symptoms.

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